

Employee Empowerment and Organizational Commitment: A Multiple Linear Regression

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Abstract: *This study aimed to determine the influence of structural and psychological empowerment on organizational commitment among employees from the Commission on Higher Education Regional Offices situated in Mindanao, Philippines. This study utilized inferential statistics, specifically multiple linear regression, in analyzing and interpreting data gathered through the total enumeration sampling method for all 145 employees. The study showed that among the components of structural and psychological empowerment, only perceived support and competence cognition has a positive influence on organizational commitment, further proving that as an employee's level of perceived support and competence cognition increases and also employees' level of commitment to the organization.*

Keywords: employee empowerment, multiple linear regression, organizational commitment, Philippines

I. INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is on the verge of political re-awakening; hence, present political leadership require government agencies to move hastily congruent to the direction it precedes. Relative to these challenges, new management approaches must be explored specifically to augment the present pressure of providing efficient and effective service to the stakeholders, especially the public.

However, it is a wide-ranging truth that there is no perfect formula for effective management approach hence organizations face difficulty in developing committed employees. According to Maina (2016), committed employees are empowered employees and empowering public service employees benefits public organizations and the general public as well.

In the study conducted by Manyal (2015) aimed at determining various factors affecting the level of organizational factors across the globe, specifically India, Nigeria, United States of America, United Kingdom, Dutch, and Singapore, she found out that there is positive relation between job satisfaction and innovative and supportive organizational culture as it leads to productivity and profitability by reducing absenteeism and employee turnover as it provide a scope to an employee to take initiative risk to do something new for the betterment of an organization in terms of working. Further, she emphasized that it is important for management to be considerate of various factors that implicate and sustain organizational commitment in employees.

In the Philippines, Nacpil and Lacap (2018) found out that government employees in Region III exhibit relatively significant level of commitment which may be translated into faithfulness to work ethic, commitment to their own jobs, and involvement commitment, among others. In the same study, they found out that it is vital for any organization to concentrate on the positive relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment, since they can impact organizational performance.

The Commission on Higher Education, a national agency mandated to regulate and develop the higher education system of the Philippines is of no exemption to the demands of providing efficient and effective organizational performance, the same is expected from its employees. Therefore, this study is conducted to assess empowerment factors and how it influences the organizational commitment of employees from CHED Regional Offices in Mindanao.

II. METHODOLOGY

A non-experimental quantitative research design was utilized in the conduct of the study, using the descriptive-correlational technique. Data collection using the descriptive method focuses on discovering the nature of the specific events under study. It may include minimal to moderate, structured, open-ended, individual, or focus group interview. It may also include observations, and examination of records, reports, photographs, and documents. Unlike other qualitative approaches, data analysis of descriptive research does not use pre-existing set of rules that have been explored and generated from the philosophical or epistemological stance (Lambert & Lambert, 2012). This type of research is more concerned with “what” rather than how or why something has happened (Nasaji, 2015).

Likewise, correlational research is employed to test the degree of relationship between two or more variables (Subia et al, 2018). Findings from this method can be used to determine and explore prevalence and relationships among variables, and to forecast events from current or an existing data. In spite of its many uses, a better assumption is required when using the methodology and analysis of data (Curtis, Comiskey & Dempsey, 2016). Multi-linear regression analysis, specifically Stepwise Regression, was used in the analysis of data gathered during the conduct of the study specifically to test the statistical significance of the independent variable (structural empowerment and psychological empowerment) and dependent variable (organizational commitment). This type of statistical tool is appropriate for this kind of study as it allows multiple independent variable to be part of the regression model. In the study, the hypotheses were set at 95% level of confidence.

III. RESULTS

The following discussion shows the result of the influence tests that aim to determine the significant influence of structural empowerment and psychological empowerment to the organizational commitment of employees from the CHED Regional Office in Mindanao. With the basis on the derived result, only perceived support for structural empowerment and competence cognition for psychological empowerment were found to have significant influence over employee organizational commitment.

Table 1 below shows the significant variables and its corresponding percentage of influence to organizational commitment based on the computed R2 and adjusted R2. Model 1 presents the influence of competence cognition to organizational commitment at 19.2 percent to 19.8 percent. Whereas model 2 depicts the influence of perceived support to organizational commitment at 22.5 percent to 23.7 percent.

Table 1: Influence of Structural and Psychological Empowerment to Organizational Commitment

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.445 ^a	.198	.192	.4958248
2	.486 ^b	.237	.225	.4856859

a. Predictors: (Constant), Competence
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Competence, Perceived Support

Table 2 shows the models of beta coefficients for the significant variables, where model 1 shows competence cognition with beta coefficient (B) = .458, t-value = 5.669 at P = .000 which is lower than .05 explains that the .458 increase on organizational commitment is attributed to cognitive competence.

In model 2, competence cognitive has B = .341, t-value = 3.726 at P = .000; perceived support is added with B = .181, t-value = 2.546 at P = .000 which is an implication that an increase in the level of organizational commitment by .341 and .181 is attributable to the combination of competence cognition and perceived support.

Table 2: Factors of Structural and Psychological Empowerment that Influences Organizational Commitment

	Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.684	.344		4.894	.000
	Competence	.458	.081	.445	5.669	.000
2	(Constant)	1.480	.347		4.270	.000
	Competence	.341	.091	.331	3.726	.000
	Perceived Support	.181	.071	.227	2.546	.012

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Commitment

The result of the study affirms the findings of several studies relating to structural and psychological empowerment to organizational commitment, further supports the study of Maina (2016) which showed that co-workers and supervisors’ support contributes significantly to influencing organizational commitment. Likewise, psychological empowerment where all aspects of psychological empowerment including competence cognition showed a positive relationship with organizational commitment.

IV. CONCLUSION

The result of the study revealed that among the four components of structural empowerment, only the employee’s perception of support has significant influence to level of organizational commitment. Relative to the respondents’ level of psychological empowerment, among the four components, it was found out that only competence cognition has positive influence to an employees’ commitment to his organization. Further proving that as an employees’ level of perceived support and competence cognition increases, the level of commitment to the organization also increases.

Relative to the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been presented: (1) It is important that the management enhance mentoring and coaching activities to employees that are found to be non-performing or may only be performing satisfactorily. It is also recommended to amplify the creation of small support groups headed by a trained person to handle employee personal challenges that may affect job performance. This group could plan trainings and practical exposure to employees in order to gain high level of competence towards the fulfillment of assigned tasks. This may also include strengthening the Commission’s scholarship programs to regular employees, not just to pursue graduate courses but also to include technical or skill courses, as these too may further elevate an employee’s competency level. (2) Academe may use the result of this study in their Human Resource Management course as basis in the further study of the program. And (3) future researchers may study further the challenges faced by the employees regardless of industry, in order to sustain the feeling of empowerment of employees that affects its commitment to the organization and ultimately, the performance of the operation.

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